

Project report – AM 4 Industry

Design in Additive Manufacturing

Basic considerations related to processes

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1 Introduction

Additive manufacturing (AM) is said to be able to produce all geometries. Designers tend to propose amazing geometries but are often disappointed with the component quality. Components can be deformed, have poor surface quality, can be less clean than expected or outside the tolerances.....

Designers can do something to address these problems. Some basic considerations would enable them to make their components much easier to produce. If production is easier, the final quality is improved and sometimes there is even a reduction in cost without sacrificing performance.

The purpose of this document is to provide an introduction to how the various AM machines work. This will help the reader understand why there are some design rules in AM and why they exist.

In this way, designers can create optimised shapes for the selected AM technology. This means better as-built quality and less expensive post-treatment.

This work was carried out by the Sirris Research Centre¹ as part of the Cornet project AM4I – Additive Manufacturing for Industries².

1.1 Why use additive manufacturing (AM)?

The use of “traditional/conventional” technologies (e.g. machining and injection moulding) has many advantages. All subtractive techniques (EDM, turning, milling,..) can provide a reflective surface finish and micron-accurate part accuracy on almost all available materials. Injection moulding has quite a long set-up, but once it is fixed, the production volume (parts production per time unit) is very high, which is usually the only way to mass production.

But the challenges facing the industry are becoming increasingly complicated, so much so that sometimes the geometry that meets a particular challenge is simply not feasible with conventional techniques. Sometimes this is due to the accessibility of the tool in machining or to the fact that the mould must be opened in injection moulding to retrieve the part without damaging it. Sometimes it is simply because the production is too small (a single prototype) to be cost-effective and justify the tooling costs involved.

¹ <https://www.sirris.be/>

² <http://am4industry.azurewebsites.net/>

Figure 1: Basic design rules used in injection moulding to face limitations

Figure 2: Problem of tool accessibility during machining, which reduces the achievable geometric complexity.

The rather severe limitations mentioned above can prevent parts from becoming lighter, more efficient and faster, or early prototypes from being able to be used much earlier to repeat and improve them. In addition, in terms of costs, the capabilities of traditional technologies can be roughly summarised, and the opportunities associated with additive manufacturing emerge:

Figure 3: Cost-effective opportunities (green areas) for AM, compared to conventional manufacturing

Figure 3 shows what is useful in conventional manufacturing (CM) and what is economically of greater interest when using additive manufacturing (AM).

In respect of the number of parts produced in the traditional way, it is well known that the more identical the parts that are produced by a machine, the cheaper the unit costs. If the quantity to be produced decreases too much, tooling costs can make production unaffordable and unprofitable. This is represented by the blue curve, the dotted limit indicating where the number of parts produced becomes too low.

In terms of geometric complexity associated with the cost of conventional machining, the tendency is more like the red curve. Low complexity means low costs, but if the part is too complex for the technology, it may become too large, or there may be no way to manufacture it for technical reasons. This limitation is represented by the red dotted line.

If AM is considered (green dashed line), the first entry point is that AM is currently quite expensive (located on the right side of the graph). On the other hand, the high price will not change as much with the number of parts produced, or in view of their complexity.

Assuming that two regions in AM are profitable when compared to conventional manufacturing:

- It is possible to make very complex parts...
- ...which are needed in small quantities.

This also means that if the selected part is elsewhere on the graph (cheaper to produce, not too complex, quite large quantities) outside the green areas, AM should not be used to produce them, otherwise it will be uneconomical, or risks concerning current AM uncertainties will be present.

Additive manufacturing (AM) can have many advantages:

- optimised design can result in significantly **less waste of material** compared to machining.
- Due to the layer-by-layer approach, the interior of a component becomes easily accessible, so that the designer can realise much more complex designs (internal cavities, lightweight structures, channels,...) than with conventional techniques.
- Manufacturing in a single step **eliminates tooling** during the manufacturing step. No mould or special device is required to position the part in a machine.
- A **wide range of materials** is already available in polymers, metals and ceramics.
- Roughly speaking, **geometric complexity does not increase costs**. In other words, to make a part very light, from 3D mesh and with integrated channels and hinges would cost about the same price as a cubic block with the same height and material volume. This is absolutely not the case with conventional technologies.
- It becomes possible to produce **very different parts (size, complexity,...) in one operation** whereas a mould would only be able to produce the model for which it was designed.
- Some AM technologies can produce **parts made from different materials** in a single pass.
- Some **functionalities (springs, hinges, gears, rotating shafts,...) can be integrated** into the design. This does not require any post-assembly steps, but can be done directly from the AM machine.
- The delay in producing **a standard volume (300x300x400 mm³) is usually less than a week**, from scratch and CAD to a finished product ready for use. It is also very practical for the early iterative development of a product that is subsequently to be injection-moulded for mass production.
- Adaptation, labelling, texturing, conformal cooling channels, weight reduction,... all become much cheaper.

But of course there are also some limitations to be aware of:

- **The best achievable geometric accuracy is 0.1 mm** on standard AM machines, for a part smaller than 100 mm. Above this length, 0.1% must be taken into account. Depending on material, technology and component bulk, this value can even reach 0.3 %. For this reason, post-processing is often necessary locally.
- The **maximum component size limitation** can prevent the designer from producing large parts such as car bumpers or tables in a single operation using standard technologies. On average, the maximum size achievable on industrial machines is currently about 800 mm. But some non-standard techniques can produce a 4000x2000x1000 mm sand mould, or even houses with concrete walls, or a small vehicle hull from a “polymer + carbon” extruder moving along the XYZ.

- Many AM technologies require a **supporting structure**. Roughly speaking, this structure connects the component to the building platform. It prevents the components from moving during manufacturing. It is built by the machine at the same time as the parts themselves. Unfortunately, this structure must be removed after manufacture and this requires a finishing step to remove the support from the parts. This structure is described in more detail in *section2.3*.
- Immediately after manufacture, **the raw material is everywhere**, around the parts, in cavities, crevices, channels, holes,... and if the design does not take this into account, it can be very difficult to remove this raw material from narrow spaces (see *section2.2*)
- Some techniques produce parts with **anisotropic mechanical properties**, especially cheap machines and “huge” layer thicknesses ($> 100 \mu\text{m}$). With most AM technologies, however, this mechanical anisotropy is not very pronounced.

A good designer is the most valuable resource in the AM world. He is able to adapt the shape of the part to meet requirements, but will also be able to take into account all the factors that facilitate manufacture and post-processing.

Efficient and easy-to-produce design is the only way to make AM profitable.

1.2 What guidance is there for the design of complex shapes?

Now that AM is opening up a universe of achievable geometric complexities, designers are becoming rich, a bit like people with too much money: they don't realise what new and interesting things can be made with it. Fortunately, there are some software developments that have made topological optimisation possible.

To simplify matters, the goal of this kind of software is to distribute a predefined amount of material in a given available volume in order to optimise the response to a certain load case by maximising criteria like stiffness. The output of such software is a voxelisation of the specified volume, where each voxel has a calculated density (from 100% – full density – for the most critical voxels, to 0% – empty volume – for the less participative ones). The user then chooses which density value should be the trigger. For example, he could decide that the triggered density should be 50%. Each voxel with a density above 50% would be set to full density, and each voxel with a value below 50% would be considered empty. This process produces very organic shapes with optimal mass distribution. The mould must then be tested in the FEM to check its behaviour under the load. If it is not optimised (too safe, heavy or too thin), then an iteration loop must be examined to change the density trigger and consider more or less material. An example of an improvement in part weight is shown in *Figure 4*:

Figure 4: Topological optimisation (right side, shown in white) of a conventionally made one (left side, shown in dark grey) - courtesy of Ronchi³

In addition, all manufacturing problems are associated with thermal flow through the part during the process, or with the overhanging area. An efficient way to facilitate the manufacture of AM components and reduce post-processing through design measures is to imagine that water must flow as freely as possible through the (imaginary hollow) component, from top to bottom at a selected position, at each layer. Below are just a few examples.

³ <https://www.sirris.be/success-story/grip-component-ronchi-capping-machine-goes-3d-diet>

Figure 5: “Top-down water flow” way of thinking to anticipate thermal problems in AM.

To explain briefly: if the "L-shaped" part in *Figure 5* has to be manufactured, several positions in the machine can be selected. For position 1, the cross-section in the first layers is quite large. So there is a lot of energy to provide [J/mm²] to melt the powder, and a lot to get to the platform. When comparing the “top-down water flow”, imagine that the part is hollowed out so that it becomes a pipe with the same cross section. There is proportionally a lot of water to evacuate (because of the large cross section), which could lead to “overflow” (overheating) if there is a large area (a lot of energy to disperse) or a constriction of the pipe somewhere below the current layer. This is sometimes a risky situation, but the design and chosen alignment can cope with it. In the next steps of position 1 it becomes easier (straight down, no necking, little energy input), so in this configuration everything should be fine, even if the early phases need to be carefully checked.

In position 2, the initial and middle layers would be quite simple (constant section, less energy input), but would cause many problems in the final layers. The section for evacuating the “overflow” is much thinner than the input section. Moreover, the change is very sudden, and the “droplets” from the left side of the overhanging area are not properly evacuated. This “droplet” accumulation, which is understood on the basis of “water flow” considerations, is translated in the actual process as heat accumulation, i.e. an overheating effect that leads to blockage of the area and possible delamination / twisting of this section of the component.

The AM designer's goal is to draw parts with “no” overhanging areas, no areas where water can accumulate, and with the thinnest areas to reduce the heat flow to be dissipated.

2 Main aspects of AM

2.1 The different technologies

There are several very different ways of manufacturing parts in additive manufacturing. ASTM currently offers them in seven categories. They are all shown at the top of the picture below:

Figure 6: Additive manufacturing families

Since they work differently, some special rules must be followed for each one of them if you intend to design a part for a selected one. Let us briefly consider the different principles:

2.1.1 Vat photopolymerisation (SLA)

The raw material in this case is a liquid, a resin, which is a photosensitive polymer. This means that when UV light from a lamp or laser touches this liquid, it solidifies locally.

The machine looks a bit like a deep fryer. The process starts with a perforated plate positioned just below (about 0.02 mm) the liquid surface and a UV laser tracks the component's cores and contours of the first layer on the plate. This polymerises / solidifies the liquid locally around the plate holes. The first layer is thus anchored to the plate. The plate is then levelled deeper into the liquid of the same amount (about 0.02 mm) to allow some resin to form a film over the previous layer. The UV laser then

polymerises layer 2 and the process is repeated until all the parts are produced. At the end, the plate is at the bottom of the resin tank and the parts are between the liquid surface and the plate. The technician can pull out the plate with the parts on it as one might do with the basket of a fryer full of chips.

Figure 7: Vat photopolymerisation principle, with laser

There are some technological differences that could be seen around this principle:

A single laser often takes a long time to process a whole layer. Therefore, a light projector with a UV lamp can also be used to process a complete surface in a single flash. Roughly speaking, this is faster than a laser, but the edges of the part may be slightly distorted depending on projector resolution, whereas the laser makes smooth curves.

A tank of resin as large as the parts you want to produce could cost a lot to fill (some resins that mimic ABS can cost around €300/litre). For this reason, some technicians prefer to apply a small amount of resin to a transparent glass under which the projector is located. It also uses a plate that moves upwards from the liquid with the solids anchored on it, rather than downwards into the resin tank.

Figure 8: Vat photopolymerisation, with DLP

The strength of this technique is the accuracy and surface quality of the part in the “as built” condition. There are no sticky powder grains on the surface, and this surface can even be transparent when built. The distortion is limited and the minimum achievable property can be up to 0.1 mm, useful for jewellery.

However, depending on the application, ageing of the material can be a problem. After a while under sunlight such a material can become more brittle than expected.

DSM Somos, one of the major AM resin manufacturers, can supply a wide range of materials with very different properties. Data sheets are available on their website⁴.

2.1.2 Material extrusion (a.k.a. fused deposition modelling – FDM)

This technology works just like toothpaste applied to a toothbrush. The raw material is an ordinary polymer (PLA, ABS, PP, PS,...), generally in wire form, and it is mechanically pressed through a heated nozzle. This causes the polymer to melt slightly. At the outlet, the molten bead is pressed onto the previous layer and the print head moves across the working area to deposit a track. The part is produced by stacking tracks.

⁴ https://www.dsm.com/solutions/additive-manufacturing/en_US/products.html

Figure 9: Material extrusion principle

This technology is very well suited to produce hollow parts such as pipes, hulls or shells. The main reason is the displacement speed of the nozzle, which is quite limited compared to a laser point driven by mirrors, which can reach a few meters per second. In order to achieve reasonable production speed, the AM family of material extrusions deposits thicker layers (> 0.1 mm) than other AM polymer technologies and tries to minimise filling the component core, even if it requires doing few external contours. The goal therefore is not to produce a full, dense part, but a hull that is thick enough to engender sufficient strength. This procedure allows bulk and massive components to be produced more quickly, load situation permitting.

The advantage of using a wire instead of powder is the surface finish, which is quite smooth even if the layer tracks are clearly visible and have significant roughness.

Powder-based AM process roughness profile

Wire-based AM process roughness profile

Figure 10: Typical roughness profiles in AM (wire-based or powder-based processes)

Moreover, since there are no sticky powder grains, the surface is very clean and is not subject to loose material residues, which is suitable when cleanliness properties are required.

Unfortunately, the minimum properties that can be achieved by material extrusion are not enormous. It is difficult to find a minimum wall thickness that is less than 1 mm and the anisotropy of mechanical properties can be quite significant compared to other AM polymer technologies.

The material spectrum for these material extrusion technologies is very broad. There are even some composite wires (polymer + fibres or metal powder mixed). Some technologies can also directly use pellets from injection moulding or metal injection moulding (MIM).

2.1.3 Material jetting

The aim is to deposit a light-sensitive liquid material (polymer) in the same way as a paper printer would do with classic ink. Inside the machine there is a print head which can pixellate the layer and choose which material is deposited in which pixel. Since it is a multi-nozzle print head, some of them can deposit a white and strong material, while others can deposit a black and ductile material. In new technologies, up to six materials can be used together, including transparent materials.

Figure 11: Material jetting principle.

This allows the user to determine the chemical composition / mechanical properties / colour / transparency /.... of any voxel of the part.

The deposited droplets are very small, so the support structure required by this technology is quite dense and narrow in order to catch the resin droplets falling from the print head. It looks more like a “foam” than a grid / 3D mesh structure. The material waste with this technology is therefore quite high in relation to the number of supports required. Fortunately, this specific support material can be removed quite easily with a water jet, even if the material is quite expansive.

The material properties are the same as for all epoxy/acrylate resins used in stereo lithography / vat photopolymerisation. The ageing of the material due to UV exposure remains a problem; the parts become more brittle over time.

The accuracy of this process is very good in the Z direction due to the levelling roller (layer thickness down to 14 μm), and the contours in the XY plane are very slightly pixellated (approx. 600 dpi resolution) compared to the smooth contour of a laser.

There are very few phenomena that affect the accuracy when using this technology. The advantages are very easy handling; no engineering knowledge is required; almost everything is automated (including the support generation) and machine collisions are rare.

2.1.4 Binder jetting

Binder jetting involves bonding the powder grains together at each layer and between two successive layers. The binder/glue is deposited as small droplets from a print head that can move over the entire working surface.

Figure 12: Binder jetting principle

Sometimes colours can be applied to the component contours parallel to the adhesive. This is applied to white powder such as plaster/gypsum. Even if the part is brittle in “as built” condition (about 40% of porosity, depending on powder size and distribution), it may be sufficient for some aesthetic demonstrations that will not be subject to manipulation. Parts can be reinforced by applying a solidifying coating, such as a resin or varnish.

Some metal parts are also made this way. To eliminate the weak aspect of the bond, two options are proposed:

The first is sintering the part in a furnace after manufacture. Sintering is a thermal process that provides the powder grains with enough energy to close the gap between them slightly. Since no material is added during sintering, there is of course significant shrinkage (over 20% volume reduction). If the part is quite small, this process can be controlled and compensated so that the final geometry is very close to the original CAD model. For larger parts, the displacement due to shrinkage is so significant that deformations occur and the part is quickly outside the tolerances. The advantage is the “single material” aspect, the good accuracy and surface quality, but almost exclusively for small parts (< 50 mm).

The second option is to infiltrate the porous “as built” material. A suitable infiltrate is selected for this purpose. This requires a material with a lower melting point than the

additively manufactured one and good wettability between the two at high temperatures. An example of this good combination is a part made in SS 316L infiltrated by bronze. Thanks to these properties, the infiltrate, not the part, melts in a furnace at high temperature. Since the latter is porous and because of good wettability, the infiltrate can penetrate the component by capillary action and close all gaps between the powder grains to achieve good final mechanical properties. This reduces shrinkage considerably and larger parts can be produced. Since the thermal input occurs in a furnace, heating and cooling are slow, minimising internal stresses. This route allows much larger parts (up to 800 mm), which are more massive and bulky, to be produced. The weakness is the “composite aspect” (not a single material) and roughness similar to sand casting.

2.1.5 Powder bed fusion

The aim in this case is selectively to melt a powder layer with a thin energy beam (laser or electron beam). When the energy point moves over the powder, a welded path is formed. In this way, all the component areas can be covered. After completion of a layer, the working plate moves downwards by a distance corresponding to the layer thickness (30 - 90 μm) and a new powder layer is applied with a wiper. The average processing time for a layer on standard machines is between 30 seconds and 2 minutes (depending on the proportion of the area to be melted). The process is repeated until the parts are completely manufactured.

2.1.5.1 Metal powder melt with a laser (LBM)

Figure 13: Powder bed fusion (laser metal) principle

Due to this principle, the cooling of the melt pool is very high (a kind of local quenching), which leads to high thermal stresses in metals. If this is not addressed, the component is deformed by these stresses. To prevent the parts from twisting, they must be anchored / rooted in a rigid plate that is sufficiently rigid / thick not to bend. The connection between the part and the plate is the “supporting structure”, which is made by the machine during the process at the same time as the part. The aim is to create a sacrificial structure (made of the same material as the components) that is strong enough to avoid deformation, yet easy to remove mechanically after stress relief annealing. This thermal treatment is carried out after manufacture. The plate with all the parts still anchored on it is placed in a classic furnace for a stress relief cycle.

From this step, if well controlled, no residual stress remains and the part can be released with virtually no deformation. In this step, the supporting structure must be removed mechanically, which costs time and money if there are many of these supports.

This technology can propose the finest details of AM metal parts, with a minimum wall thickness of around 0.2 mm. A large range of material is available and the expected mechanical properties are roughly located between casting and forging, depending on surface finish and part density.

The disadvantage is the supporting structure. The more massive the part, the more supports are needed to prevent distortion, especially if the section is long in the horizontal plane (shrinkage section). The current size of the building chamber which laser technology can reach is 500x280x800 mm on a standard machine (SLM 800 from SLM Solutions). There are also some special sizes, e.g. the BETA from GE (ATLAS project - 1100x1100x300 mm).

2.1.5.2 Metal powder melt with an electron beam (EBM)

If the heat source is an electron beam, there are some noticeable differences. First, electron beam means vacuum conditions. Thus the machine structure is much stronger than the laser technology, which is mostly under argon atmosphere. A vacuum is also a very good thermal insulator. As a result, the machine reaches 700 - 1000°C inside the construction chamber. This results in almost “no” cooling during production, i.e. “no” thermal stress. Therefore, this process requires considerably fewer supports than laser technology, which usually works at 200°C. Its main task is to drive away the heat, not to avoid distortions. This allows bulkier parts to be achieved, but the material range is more limited (titanium, Co-Cr alloys and nickel alloys).

The disadvantages of the electron beam are the sintering of the surrounding powder (by preheating at high temperature) and a poorer surface quality (Ra 20 - 35 µm) than with laser technologies. A sintered powder is much more difficult to remove from internal cavities than an unaltered powder, which easily exits the part simply by tilting.

2.1.5.3 Polymer powder melt with a laser (SLS)

When powder bed is applied to polymer materials such as PA, TPU, PP, PS,..., there is no need for support. This is because the temperature inside the chamber is about 95% of the melting point. There is therefore no cooling, i.e. no thermal stress. So little that the sintered powder surrounding the parts is sufficient to be the support. The direct advantage is that the parts can be stacked in the construction volume, which increases productivity. In addition, no support welded to the parts needs to be removed. However, removing the sinter powder cake surrounding the component can be tedious, especially in narrow cavities.

Figure 14: Selective laser sintering principle

In addition, the high temperature inside the machine during the process accelerates the ageing of the raw material. As an example, a new batch of powder is usually a mixture of 50% virgin + 50% recycled powders for PA12. 20% pure + 80% recycled is better for TPU. There is, of course, a cost factor.

One of the goals of a designer trying “powder bed fusion” applied to metal powders is to get rid of the supports by designing a part “without downward horizontal surfaces” (see 2.3). In other words, to design a “self-supporting” design with “no” horizontal sections.

2.1.6 Direct energy deposition

This is the exact opposite of a milling machine. When the drill removes material from a block, the multi-axis nozzle mounted on a robot or CNC machine welds successive paths together to make a part from scratch, but also to repair or coat an existing one. The raw material can be a powder or a wire made from metallic or ceramic material. Roughly speaking, this is fused deposition modelling for materials with high melting temperatures.

Figure 15: Direct energy deposition principle

A good point is the fact that this technology can work on non-flat surfaces as there is no recoater/wiper. This allows thick coatings (from 0.1 mm to a few mm) or 3D features to be applied or added to complex parts.

Moreover, the use of a powder flow blown through a nozzle instead of a wiper that distributes powder tank contents has the advantage of changing the material composition. Some valves can tune the different mass flows from different tanks, to mix them gradually during manufacture. This allows alloys with very different CTE, such as a metal and a ceramic, to be welded together. This is done by a smooth transition between the two, over a certain number of layers, which dilutes the intensity of the resulting stresses.

This technology has the same limitations as classic milling machines in terms of tool accessibility. In general, the distance between the nozzle and the part is less than 15 mm. Filling a deep groove or the inside of internal cavities can therefore be difficult.

Another point is the development of thermal history during manufacture. As the part gets hotter, the properties in the lower part differ from those in the upper part. Depending on the application, this may or may not be significant.

Process stability can be difficult to achieve, especially for an upper part consisting of a large number of layers. This is probably the reason why this technology has already implemented closed-loop control in commercial offers based on sensor measurements.

2.1.7 Sheet lamination

This is a less common technology in AM. The aim is to cut sheets of material (polymer, metal, paper,...) with the desired shape (section of the part to be produced), then stack and join them together. It is therefore a mixture of subtractive and additive manufacturing.

This is a cheap and clean technology (no powder or chemical vapour in the air). But not very popular compared to other technologies.

2.1.8 Summary

To select good AM technology, the different component requirements must be considered in order of priority. It is very difficult to meet all the criteria, so it is a case of finding the best compromise. Additionally, nothing is simple in this selection step. It is always useful to discuss the various available solutions with a specialist.

However, if a (very rough) selection guide is to be proposed to choose from the technologies described above, it might look as follows, based on the most important requirement selection.

Best surface finish “as built”: Resin-based techniques are at the forefront. Then choose between laser-based ones (metal or polymers).

To make a massive/bulky part: Avoid thermal processes with fast and strong cooling.

To make a very detailed part: Laser based techniques (first resin, then powder) are the best for such criteria.

For a minimum of post processing: Avoid technologies that require supports. The exception would be supports that are in a material other than the part itself; these may be easier to remove.

To make a part of huge dimensions: Direct energy deposition or binder jetting with infiltration can be considered. Alternatively, consider the division of the part into sub-parts that have to be reassembled.

To make an aesthetic part (no special mechanical purpose): Material jetting offers many possibilities in this field.

To make an effective part: If polymer suffices, it is usually cheaper. Therefore, SLS and FDM must be considered. Resin-based techniques are the second choice (more brittle). For metal, everything is good, but more expensive.

To make a light part full of internal cavities: Avoid techniques that produce a strong powder cake around the parts after manufacture; this can be difficult to remove in tight places. A design adjustment to avoid supports is key.

To make 100,000 parts larger than 300 mm per year: AM is not a good choice.

To make a simple part like a bulky cube: AM is not a good choice.

2.2 The raw material

As explained in the previous section, there are many ways to use additive manufacturing. The material can be used in very different configurations (powder, liquid, plate, wire, ink,...) and one of AM's main concerns is to remove it after completion of the job.

In particular, some techniques (selective laser sintering - SLS, electron beam melting - EBM) sinter the powder around the part due to the hot conditions. Sintering means that powder grains are melted on the surface and stick together as if they were partially welded in all contact zones between the grains. This state of the heat-stressed powder is called a "cake", and the manufactured parts are inside this cake. It is possible to remove this block of sintered powder manually from the manufacturing chamber. The cohesion between the powder grains is strong enough to make this possible. However, it is quite difficult to remove such a cake from narrow internal cavities.

Some illustrations will serve to show how the powder surrounds the parts after job completion in the SLS process, and how difficult it can be to clean too complex a structure.....

Figure 16: Raw material removal step, at the end of an SLS process

Sometimes the only aim of removing the raw material is to make the part as light as possible, but it can also be for reasons of hygiene and safety e.g. in medicine or aerospace, where no residues (powder grains, resin droplets,...) should be released during the life of the part. This is something really important to focus on right from the design stage.

The most obvious example is the construction of a very complex (and thus very optimised) cooling channel in a mould insert. A designer can spend hours simulating to find the ideal shape to dissipate the heat optimally after the injection step. But if he hasn't taken care of the raw material that fills the entire channel during production, his expensive design won't be usable and most of it will end up in the bin. For instance, if this mould is made of metal from a powder and the channel is about 1 mm in diameter but over two metres long, how will it be possible to remove the metal powder from this very long and narrow channel? The basic consideration about the raw material to be taken into account at the design stage is how to remove it afterwards. Here are some examples that illustrate the "raw material concern".

Imagine making a simple cube out of powder using laser melting technology like SLS, with the cube being intended to be hollow:

Figure 17: A hollowed cube to be produced

For the first layers, the powder is distributed over the entire surface and the entire square area of the cube is melted (red line in the picture below):

Figure 18: As the first layer is manufactured, all the area is processed by the laser

When the middle of the part is reached, only the vertical walls are treated with the laser, but the powder is distributed over the entire surface as usual:

Figure 19: As the mid layers are manufactured, the side walls are processed by the laser

At the end, the entire area is processed again with the laser, as with the first layers:

Figure 20: Processing of last layers seals the cube

On the last picture (*Figure 20*) it is easy to see that a large amount of the raw material remains trapped inside the cube, since obviously no outlet has been made through the skin of the cube to remove this trapped material after manufacture. In this case it was powder, but of course the issue is also applicable to resins, sheets, wires,... So, it is very important to consider the raw material in the design phase, otherwise the hollow cube will be much heavier than expected.

But it is not enough to think about ways to remove the raw material. Sometimes the outlet is too narrow, or it is not possible to remove everything due to the internal configuration, or sometimes it is not permitted to have an outlet between the inside and outside of the part. Here are some further examples to illustrate a wrong and a better configuration.

In the following case (*Figure 21*), a simple, small hole was made to avoid too much impact on the design.... but the technician will need much more time to remove the internal raw material for accessibility reasons, so that it will ultimately cost more. Also, the sharp internal edges of the cube are very good to allow better anchoring of the powder in these areas, and an iron wire is needed to try to scrape off the powder blindly in these areas. Finally, if the technician wants to suck out the powder with a vacuum cleaner, it is very difficult to do because no other outlet allows air to circulate through the part to remove the raw material. Therefore, the second thought may be better than the first. A third option could be a lot of smaller holes around the cube, through which the powder could leave the part without clogging it.

First thought

Figure 21: Design modification with "easier cleaning" considered

If the internal shape is not a "simple" volume, but a kind of complex channel, then several outlets would be required, with shapes adapted to facilitate removal. As always in AM, the designer's goal is to forget the traditional design and to start from the functions of the part to be designed, therefore the aim is to adapt the design to AM requirements. *Figure 22* is an example of "function" approach design compared to traditional design:

Figure 22: Design process starting from component functions. Comparison between traditional and AM design approach

Traditionally, the material is removed from a block of material. To make a block lighter, it would be helpful to hollow it. This makes the traditional design above very difficult to clean after AM, if it can be done at all. Because in AM the starting point is not a block but nothing, and the aim is to make it as simple as possible by trying to get rid of the cavity

and produce something functional and easy to clean, akin to the last design shown in *Figure 22*.

AM also allows designers to reduce the assembly step by integrating some moving parts such as hinges, rotary axes or springs into a single design and to have these elements assembled directly from the machine in a single process. The secret is based on the gap (approx. 0.4 mm, associated with the chosen technology) between the moving parts, which should be small to allow smooth and accurate movement. But of course some raw material will fill this gap. If there is no outlet, it would be impossible to unclog the hinge. Here are some examples:

For a ball joint, to reduce the gap between the outer and inner shell, it is advisable to perforate the outer shell to remove any remaining raw material, as shown below.

Figure 23: Ball joint with integrated powder evacuation channels in external component

If a long rotating axis is required to pass through a block, it is advisable to consider a variable gap and the accessibility of the axis centre, as shown below:

Figure 24: Axle design with powder evacuation approach

Of course, the worst cases for cleaning the raw material are heat exchangers or large lattice structures. Some preliminary tests must be carried out to test the cleanability of some samples beforehand. Below are some examples of complex but cleanable parts:

<https://www.3trpd.co.uk/>

<http://www.fit-production.de/>

Figure 25: Example of complex parts which have been successfully cleaned inside

To conclude, raw material will be everywhere. Experienced technicians can find bright ideas to remove them after the AM process, but it may be expensive and sometimes impossible. The best solution, which saves time and costs while improving the overall quality of the parts, is determined by designers who are aware of this aspect. Each solution will be case-by-case.

2.3 The supporting structure

This is the necessary evil that unfortunately is very common in AM. It refers to a light structure that resembles a scaffold, which supports the part during manufacture. It is built at the same time as the parts themselves.

Figure 26 shows some examples of parts with a common supporting structure:

Figure 26: Examples of supporting structure proportion compared to actual part volume

This structure (deep red at the bottom left on *Figure 27*) is completely defined by the positioning of the part and related to its design. The supports connect all “horizontal” surfaces visible from the bottom (“downward facing”) of the part to the working plate of the machine. This plate is represented by the brown/yellow plane in *Figure 27*. Based on an initial positioning in the machine volume space, the coloured areas will require supports because they are considered “horizontal”. Roughly speaking, this means that their normal angle with the vertical direction (Z axis of the machine) is less than 30°:

Figure 27: Highlighted areas where supports will be needed, based on chosen part orientation

The supported 3D file can be generated automatically and quickly with specially developed software and is then treated as a part by the machine. However, some expertise are required to customise the proposed support configuration and make it more efficient to facilitate future post processes and ensure process stability.

2.3.1 Why do we need supports in AM?

The supporting structure has three main roles:

- Support the layers:

Let's start with an example. If the goal is to produce a "T" shape of 150 mm width that is based on a liquid material (resin), then the first layer of the horizontal bar is 0.02 mm high and 150 mm wide. It is so thin that when the wiper levels the liquid surface, it completely deforms this very weak layer. To avoid deformation, the scaffold formed from the first layer serves as reinforcement on all "horizontal" surfaces.

Figure 28: Supports reinforce the first layer

Figure 29 is an example of supports used specially for this purpose:

Figure 29: Example of actual supports reinforcing parts in an SLA process

Figure 30 shows what happened when insufficient load-bearing structures were placed under overhang/horizontal sections in FDM.

Figure 30: Effect of missing support on overhanging areas. The longer, the worse

- Evacuate heat downwards

In thermal processes, a heat source (electron beam, IR laser beam, heating resistors,...) usually melts the powder of the current layer, to fuse all the grains in a liquid state locally to create bulk and form a continuous layer. To solidify, the heat must be dissipated after fusing, but the powder material is very close to a thermal insulator due to gas between the grains. Since the part is surrounded by powder, heat dissipation would be very slow

and inhomogeneous, resulting in very poor melt quality. The supporting structure is a solid, pore-free material, i.e. a better heat conductor, which allows the heat energy to reach the underlying production plate quite quickly, then to be evacuated in the rest of the machine itself.

Figure 31 is an example of an area where no supports have been added, resulting in local overheating / excessive melting. The upper part of the hole collapses due to excess energy. On the left side of the image the parameters were constant. On the right side, the heat input was controlled (reduced) to reduce the excessive melt effect:

Figure 31: Bad thermal evacuation, leading to part collapse, due to missing supporting structure

Figure 32 shows how the surface quality is also linked to the maximum horizontal length without supports (“overhang area”) for a given parameter set:

Figure 32: Impact of overhanging length on the quality of downward-facing surfaces, due to lack of support, resulting in poor heat dissipation.

If the overhanging area is small enough, the heat flux can easily be divided into the nearby vertical columns. When the area becomes larger, the “thermal conductive flow” is too far to reach; heat accumulates which eventually leads to overheating.

Figure 33 shows that the closer to the horizontal plane a surface is without support, the worse the surface quality, due to remelting and poor heat dissipation, especially in the metal powder bed fusion process.

Figure 33: Impact of surface orientation on the surface quality.

- Avoidance of deformations in thermal processes

The production of a part from metal powder with a heat source means that the initial layers are strongly compressed during the processing of the layers that follow. To explain it roughly, the layers that follow naturally shrink after manufacture as they cool, which creates compression over all the previous ones. This means that the longer the part is in the horizontal plane, the higher the compressive forces, which are proportional to the length between two points joined by the welded material of the current layer.

As an example, *Figure 34* shows two different layer configurations viewed from above. On the left side, the welded areas are quite small (not too large a local energy input) and not very long, regardless of the direction (so, little shrinkage). On the right side it is the other way round; many more residual stresses occur.

Figure 34: Top view of two different layer configurations. The left configuration is more robust (small maximum length and area for each “island”). The configuration on the right is the worst.

These compression forces tend to warp the part if nothing is done to prevent it. Cracking/delamination almost always starts at the outer edges of the part. For this reason, in thermal (especially metal) AM processes, especially on the outer edges of wide parts, the brackets are quite robust, with a strong connection between the part and the rigid manufacturing plate. In this way, due to its strength, the plate prevents any deformation of the part during the process if the supports are strong enough. After production and de-powdering, heat treatment can be carried out on the plate in a furnace, with the parts still welded on to reduce internal stresses. After this post-process, the parts can be released without warping.

Figure 35 shows some examples of structures that were not strong enough to withstand the residual stresses generated. They break during production and allow the part to warp freely.

Figure 35: Part delamination during the process due to the weak supporting structure, which cannot counteract the internal thermal stresses.

All these examples demonstrate the need to use supports in order to obtain accurate and high quality parts from the AM technologies that require supports (i.e. all except binder jetting and laser sintering of polymers at high temperatures).

2.3.2 Why do we want to get rid of supports?

The supports have to be removed after production, and this creates a problem. A strong support prevents warping and improves manufacturing conditions, especially if the component is not homogeneous. But a weak support is much easier to remove, which reduces the overall cost of the component.... However, the job is more likely to fail, especially with less ductile materials (such as high carbide steels) or less heat-dissipating materials (such as titanium).

In AM polymer technologies such as material extrusion (also known as fused deposition modelling) or material jetting, some supports can simply dissolve in water overnight due to the possibility of using multi-materials. In these cases the support only incurs extra material costs and not extra post-processing expense. But when working with metal,

supports and parts are made of the same material and are strongly welded together. The support in this case is much more difficult to remove. A machining centre is almost always needed when grippers, saws, chisels and hammers are found to be unsuitable.

Based on the initial design and positioning, supports may be required in areas of the part that are very difficult to access, such as internal cavities. These locations may not be accessible with a tool, so the supports will unavoidably remain there. Sometimes this creates a problem (increase in weight, danger of powder release during the life of the part,...) and sometimes it does not (support incorporated into the component design). Here is an example of supports that are hidden from a single opening and which are therefore very difficult to remove. A design solution should be investigated to avoid this situation.

Figure 36: Example of design adaptation to facilitate the removal of the support afterwards

Supports must often be well attached to the component in order to avoid distortion. During removal, it is quite common for some fragments of the supports to remain on the surface. In addition, the surface is not always flat (which would be easy to work with post-process), but sometimes very complex. In this case, it is difficult to achieve a perfect finish on these surfaces.

Figure 37: Impact of the support connections on the surface quality in the area - 1

Figure 38: Impact of the support connections on the surface quality in the area – 2

For this reason, different solutions can be chosen based on the component alignment. The first is to move critical areas upwards. This makes them less rough and more accurate in the “as built” state. But the surface on the opposite side will remain irregular. Sometimes this may be acceptable.

If it is not, then critical areas can be reworked to control overall quality. This adds extra thickness. Due to this, they can be aligned downwards, in contact with the support. Also, the quality of the other surfaces will be better.

2.3.3 What can designers do?

Even if designers are not supposed to generate the supporting structure of the parts they want to manufacture, they could significantly reduce costs if they are able to reduce the support required to manufacture a part. They need “only” avoid “horizontal” downward-facing surfaces, make a self-supporting part or integrate the supports into the design to avoid post-processing steps to remove them. Roughly speaking, it is recommended to stay above the 45° angle compared to the horizontal plane, as in *Figure 39*. Of course, if a value higher than 45° can be taken, it would improve the surface quality.

Figure 39: Main design tip in AM. To design parts as “vertically” as possible.

Here are some inspiring examples:

Beer opener - <http://resources.renishaw.com/>

<https://www.imperialmachine.com/>

Figure 40: "Vertical" designs, specially adapted to AM, reducing the need of a supporting structure

Since a long, continuous and straight line of welded material generates much more stress than a short one, it is recommended to divide the largest lengths (>100mm) in the horizontal plane (depending on the final component alignment). This means that lighter supports are needed, resulting in less post-processing steps and costs.

Figure 41: Redraw long horizontal length in shorter segment to avoid high stresses (proportional to the straight length) that would result in warping.

In conclusion, the most suitable models for AM regarding the supporting structures aspect are those that are uniformly “thin” or divided into thin islands on each horizontal section. It is also easier to produce components that are “long” in the vertical direction, since they have more possibilities in terms of self-support.

2.4 Surface quality

Surface quality is linked to several characteristics. It can be affected by the raw material morphology (powder grains can adhere to the surface, a liquid cannot), by process deviations (e.g. local overheating), by the selected component alignment (impacts the supporting structure) and, of course, by the layer thickness applied.

2.4.1 Impact of the raw material

When using powder as a raw material, the surface roughness is usually higher than with other material morphologies. This is linked to the way the boundaries of parts are treated. In powder bed technology, processing can be done with an adhesive that sticks the grains together, or by a heat source that melts them. Due to the discontinuity of the raw material, the surface is less sharp than expected. The following picture shows a zoom around the area of the component's surface.

Figure 42: Impact of partially fused powder grains on the surface, increasing roughness

During melting / glueing, all partially affected powder grains remain on the surface and produce a roughness that is proportional to the grain size range used. Depending on powder morphology and layer thickness, the tip-to-tip distance can be up to 200 μm . These pictures illustrate the actual situation:

Figure 43: Actual surface morphology of powder bed fusion process of metallic powders

If a liquid (such as a resin) is used as a raw material, the effect described above is of course almost non-existent and the surface is much smoother, thanks to the continuity of the liquid. In the image below, some zooms are performed on the surface of a stereo lithography component. The “step effect”, linked to process parameters, is clearly seen

in the thick layers. Nevertheless, the surface is very smooth; there are “no” irregularities. SLA parts can therefore be transparent even when just out of the machine.

<http://pubs.rsc.org/>

Figure 44: Impact of layer thickness on surface quality, mainly responsible for "step effect"

In resin technology with “droplet separation” the surface is less glossy. The contour lines are somewhat less smooth and more like “dotted”, but still very good in quality compared to other principles.

With a wire, like in FDM, each layer contour is itself smooth, but there is a quite significant roughness through the layers (see *Figure 10*). This is mainly due to the large minimum layer thickness of at least 0.1 mm. Here is a zoom that compares a part in FDM and SLA

with the same layer thickness of 0.1mm, in both cases on a small component (which is advantageous for SLA and not for FDM).

Figure 45: Impact of technology choice. Layer thickness is the same: FDM at left side, SLA at right side

Technologies using sheet metal have a surface quality that is linked to the raw material, which in turn depends on how the contours of the sheet metal are cut.

2.4.2 Impact of process deviation

This refers to some processes that are quite stable during production. Processes using resins (SLA, material jetting) or powder adhesives (binder jetting) are examples. But it is not the same for thermal processes. This can be understood from thermal history.

The heat is like a fluid flowing from hot spots (e.g. the melt pool) to cold spots (e.g. the machine frame, through the base plate). The greater the temperature difference, the faster it moves. And the heat also flows faster in bulk materials (the components) than through the powder, which acts as a thermal insulator between the grains due to gas. Based on these simple considerations, it is easy to understand that some configurations can cause changes during a job:

If the job consists of several small parts and a tall one (*Figure 46*), the laser needs more time to process the first layers than the last. This defines a cooling time between two layers of the tallest part, which is longer at the bottom and very short at the top. This results in heat accumulation, which can lead to overheating, and the upper area can have more defects (spherical gas pores) than the lower area. This can of course apply both to multiple parts and to a single part with a variable cross-section along the building direction.

Figure 46: Impact of layer density change on thermal history

Figure 47: Transition line between long (bottom) and short (top) cooling time due to ending of smaller parts.

Due to the component alignment, a defect like the well-known “shrinkage line” can also occur. This happens when there is a connection between two separate thin (= flexible) branches coming from below. Before the connection, the shrinkage occurs at the “small” sections of the individual branches, i.e. there is no particular geometric deviation. But at the joining layer, the section to be welded becomes much larger (the addition of the two branches’ cross-sections). Therefore the shrinkage is more important (proportional to the length) and pulls the tips of the branches together. Since branches are quite flexible (long

and thin), they bend and there is a local geometric contraction that occurs on this layer. The next layers will not suffer this phenomenon because the connection has already been made. So, only one horizontal contraction line remains. The steps are summarised in *Figure 48*.

Figure 48: successive steps which generate a "shrinkage line"

Finally, if a wide area is processed at a certain location, it could locally produce extra thickness of the material due to excessive melting. If so, it may lift or slightly damage the recoater when the powder is applied. This event results in a thicker layer of powder that can melt unevenly. This is visible on the part afterwards. It looks like a shrinkage line, but is actually due to poor powder distribution.

Figure 49: Line visible due to local non-homogeneous powder distribution, resulting in bad melt quality

2.4.3 Impact of layer thickness

Of course, the greater the layer thickness, the rougher the surface... But the process is faster, too. Therefore a compromise between the final quality and the cost & time aspects has to be chosen. Here are some examples of the same technology with different layer thicknesses:

Figure 50: Impact of layer thickness on surface quality... and manufacturing time

If the layer thickness falls below $80\ \mu\text{m}$, the “step effect” tends to be less important for the surface quality than, for example, the powder grain size. For a technology with large powder grains, it is therefore not recommended to use a smaller layer thickness to improve surface quality.

In addition, the “step effect” on “almost horizontal” surfaces becomes more obvious. There are of course geometrical reasons for this.

<http://3dpirkanmaa.fi>

Figure 51: Area where the “step effect” occurs due to part geometry

2.4.4 How can the design incorporate surface quality?

With a heat-source-based machine, the distance between the top of the highest agglomerate and the bottom of the deepest valley can be about 0.2 mm in terms of surface roughness, with the powder range being between 20 and 60 μm . This means that if a post-processing operation is carried out to produce a mirror polish (without pore) on the surface, then a skin approximately 0.2 mm thick must be removed in a post-process (machining, tribo-finishing, electrochemical polishing,...). Therefore, this extra thickness should be integrated into the design if the “zero pore on the surface” characteristic is important for the intended application.

But supposing not all surfaces of the part require such finishing. The first step in this case is to redefine the quality required for each surface. Sometimes, in the past, tolerances were determined with little knowledge, involving a significant safety risk. This had to be addressed, because the tolerances have not been reviewed since then. If tolerances can be relaxed, less rework would be required and the component would become cheaper.

Usually, the “as built” quality for the entire component is approved for a specific AM technology and the few critical areas where a seal or connection to another component is required are machined post-process.

In order to avoid any possible process deviations, the aim is to help ensure that each section has the same area to be processed and is as homogeneous as possible. Easier said than done.

The only way to manage the “step effect” without touching the machine parameters and the design is, of course, to change the alignment of the component, to transfer the roughness of the part to somewhere else.

2.5 Accuracy

Accuracy is also a huge topic in AM. Many phenomena occur during manufacture which can cause distortions (shrinkage due to cooling or polymerisation, internal stresses causing delamination, laser penetration into the bed...) or poor surface quality (high degree of roughness), as explained in the previous sections. In view of this, it is very difficult to ensure geometric accuracy better than 0.1% with the most accurate standard technology, regardless of component shape. Usually, it is wise to consider an accuracy of 0.2%. This means that a part with a dimension of 100 mm is built with a length of 100 ± 0.2 mm. These tolerances are correct if everything goes well. However, if there is a problem (e.g. column delamination due to high residual stresses), then local distortion can reach a higher value...

The designer can add extra thickness in critical areas, which is then machined to reach the final tolerances. But this increases costs, especially if the part is far from geometrical/cubic. In addition, with organic/optimised shapes, it is much more difficult to fix them in a milling machine (no flat surface) or set a reference frame for the coordinates.

Of course, in order to help with the post-processing step, the designer can add some temporary functions to make it easier to fix the part, as well as reinforcements to avoid the vibrations that can occur when machining “long and thin” structures, typical in AM.

This is why another type of tool has recently appeared on the market: AM software for simulating thermal processes. The various available commercial solutions make the calculation time very reasonable (between one and ten hours for 200 mm high organic satellite antennas). From this calculation, the mechanical distortions and the thermal history (essentially the mechanical properties) can be assessed. This type of complex calculation prevents the start of a job that could fail after three days of production due to unexpected support delamination.

With this tool, the designer can quickly check (based on the desired calculation accuracy) whether his final design is “process safe” or not, and can potentially correct it if it is not. This can save a lot of time and money considering that a titanium part of this size can easily cost up to €3000.

In addition, this software can suggest a compensated model of the design in anticipation of any distortions. This means that the distortions that occur during production would bend the compensated model in such a way as to maintain the appearance of the original design.

The tool can help manufacturers and designers to achieve the expected final accuracy.

The cost of this software is currently between 12-15,000 €/year.

2.6 Time aspects

The strength of additive manufacturing lies in producing a small volume (300X300x400 mm) in a relatively short time (about four days - 30" to 1' 30" per layer) compared to other technologies, and this from scratch, starting from a final CAD file and a piece of raw material.

Less than four days to produce several different complex parts is not possible in machining or injection moulding. In a context of small or very small series, with a very short time window, it is therefore of interest especially for the custom market. This gain

in time is already a source of profit for some companies, making the expense of AM parts more acceptable.

Sometimes AM is also used at the product development phase, not to produce the final parts, but to quickly define the optimal mould for injection moulding production. By quickly finding the initial design from current versions, some errors can be avoided at an early stage. This also saves time.

Of course, four days to make two buckets is not acceptable. So these would still be produced by injection moulding, like many other conventional parts / shapes.

The design steps can also be a time-consuming factor. Since AM is only economically interesting if the part is “special” or particularly efficient compared to a traditional design, the design step is most important. Designing the most efficient part possible requires different software and a lot of process knowledge.

It is important to know when to choose AM and when to choose another process.

3 Impact on design

The procedure for designing an AM process should almost always be the same, regardless of the technology at the beginning. The first step is always to define the functions of the component and how far the surrounding elements can be integrated, to avoid assembly effort. Whether the function is a channel to drive a fluid from one point to another, an anchorage point for a screw or axle, a hinge or a strong connection between several points to keep the distance between them constant, the goal is first to obtain a clear 3D map of these features. Here is an example of a component with a structural role (anchorage points) through which some fluids (A & B) must pass through pipes while additionally, an air duct should be integrated:

Figure 52: Definition of the 3D map of the component functions

The available space / volume (in red hatching on the previous image) is defined by surrounding elements. A first draft of the component fulfilling all the initial functions can be suggested based on minimal mechanical resistance requirements.

Figure 53: First simplified design proposition

The next step is the optimisation of the “self-supporting” (to avoid supporting structures), “easy cleaning” and post machining aspects.

With regard to the self-supporting aspect, the adjustment of the component's alignment can itself sometimes change the number of supports required:

Figure 54: same design but different alignment can change the amount of supports needed, and hence the importance of the post-process steps needed.

Mostly, however, a local re-design should be investigated to integrate the supporting structure for a selected alignment.

Figure 55: Adaptation of the design for the chosen orientation to minimise post-process operations.

4 Conclusions

AM is not suited to manufacture all parts. The first aim is to select the most promising parts, or to re-design more conventional parts with a high degree of freedom.

Then a simplifying step considering all the functions of the part down to the most basic needs to be investigated.

Based on these results, the alignment of the component in the machine is chosen, so that it is longer than wide, for the physical reasons described in this document.

Once component alignment has been chosen, the material can be added to connect the various elements in the most efficient way, due mainly to topological optimisation.

This initial design can then be optimised to reduce / split areas of horizontal sections (in order to reduce heat input and the corresponding residual stresses) and also to check the surface orientation (to avoid supports as much as possible).

An FEM analysis can be performed to check the component toughness in view of the applied load case.

Between the different steps some iterations can be performed to achieve optimum component efficiency for manufacturability and use.